

Effect of Crystal Structures on the Carbon Dioxide (CO₂) Adsorption Capacities of Calcium Oxide Based Adsorbents

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Abstract

In this paper, the effect of crystal structures on the carbon dioxide (CO₂) adsorption capacities of different calcium oxide (CaO) based adsorbents was investigated. Different CaO-based adsorbents such as calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) and calcite (CaCO₃) were synthesized by precipitation and sol-gel methods. Natural limestone (CaCO₃) was collected from Taunggyi, Southern Shan State, Myanmar. The crystal structures and morphologies of synthetic as well as natural CaO-based adsorbents were studied by X-Ray Diffractometer (XRD) and field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM). Nano/micro-structured Ca(OH)₂ was observed by precipitation method. Meanwhile, CaCO₃ nanoparticles were found by sol-gel method. Thermal properties and CO₂ adsorption capacities of CaO-based adsorbents were investigated by thermogravimetry analysis (TG-DTA). The results indicated that CO₂ adsorption capacity of CaO adsorbent obtained from Ca(OH)₂ was obviously higher than that of CaO adsorbents derived from calcite (CaCO₃) and natural limestone (CaCO₃).

Keynote: carbon dioxide, calcium oxide, adsorbents, adsorption capacity

Introduction

Since the beginning of the Industrial Revolution (1750-1850), the concentration of global atmospheric carbon dioxide (CO₂) has increased from 280 ppm (parts per million) to 350 ppm (the upper safety limit of atmospheric CO₂ level) in 1988 and now over 400 ppm (CO₂.earth, 2016). The increasing concentration of CO₂ leads to the global warming and climate change. Therefore, to reduce the emission of CO₂ into the atmosphere has been worldwide concern. One of the most indicated technologies to reduce CO₂ emission is CO₂ capture, storage and utilization (CCSU) technique (Herzog, 2001; Akgornpeak et al., 2014).

Calcium oxide (CaO) is one of the best adsorbents for CO₂ capture when compared to other solid adsorbents such as amine-based materials, activated carbon, zeolite and oxide materials. Some advantages of CaO adsorbents are reversible carbonation/calcination reactions ($CaO + CO_2 \leftrightarrow CaCO_3$), high CO₂ adsorption capacity and widely available in natural minerals (e.g. limestone (calcite), aragonite and dolomite) (Martavaltzi and Lemonidou, 2008; Sedghkerdar et al., 2014).

Some researchers studied the CO₂ adsorption performances of CaO adsorbents derived from synthesized micro/nano-sized CaCO₃ samples and CaCO₃ nanopods (Florin and Harris, 2009; Yang et al., 2009; Luo et al., 2012). On the other hand, other research groups investigated the CO₂ adsorption performances of CaO adsorbents derived from Ca(OH)₂ samples (Wu et al., 2007; Materic et al., 2014).

In this study, CO₂ adsorption capacities of CaO derived from synthesized micro/nanostructured CaO based adsorbents such as calcium hydroxide Ca(OH)₂ and calcite (CaCO₃) nanoparticles as well as natural Pleatue Limestone from Taunggyi, Southern Shan State, Myanmar were investigated. The

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results showed that CaO adsorbents obtained from synthesized Ca(OH)_2 and CaCO_3 possessed higher CO_2 adsorption capacity than CaO adsorbent derived from natural limestone (CaCO_3).

Materials and Method

Synthesis of different CaO-based Adsorbents

Calcium hydroxide Ca(OH)_2 and calcite (CaCO_3) were synthesized by precipitation and sol-gel methods. Calcium acetate monohydrate ($\text{Ca(CH}_3\text{COO)}_2 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, Sigma-Aldrich), calcium nitrate tetrahydrate ($\text{Ca(NO}_3)_2 \cdot 4\text{H}_2\text{O}$, Wako), sodium hydroxide (NaOH, Sigma-Aldrich), cetyltrimethyl ammonium bromide (CTAB) ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{42}\text{BrN}$, Kanto Chemical) and citric acid monohydrate ($\text{C}_6\text{H}_8\text{O}_7 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}$, Wako Pure Chemical) were used to synthesize different CaO-based adsorbents. Fig. 1, Fig. 2 and Fig. 3 show the methodology flow charts of the synthesis of calcium hydroxide and calcite prepared by different methods as well as the sample preparation procedure of natural limestone.

Fig. 1 Methodology flow chart of the synthesis of calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)_2) by precipitation method.

Fig. 2 Methodology flow chart of the synthesis of calcite (CaCO_3) by sol-gel method.

Fig. 3 Methodology flow chart of the preparation of fine powdered limestone.

Characterization of different CaO-based adsorbents

The synthesized CaO-based adsorbents and natural limestone were characterized by X-ray diffraction (XRD) with a Rigaku X-Ray Diffractometer using Cu $K\alpha_1$ radiation ($\lambda=0.154056$ nm). The surface morphologies were observed by Carl Zeiss SUPRA 35 VP field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM). Thermal properties of all samples were studied by using thermogravimetry analysis (TG-DTA) under N_2 gas flow.

CO₂ adsorption capacity

The CO₂ adsorption capacities of CaO-based adsorbents were carried out in a TG-DTA apparatus with Thermoplus 2 software. In this work, 800 °C was selected to conduct both carbonation and calcination reactions. A small amount of sample (~ 6.5 mg) was placed in a platinum crucible and heated from room temperature to 800 °C at a ramp rate of 10 °C/min under 100 % N_2 gas flow. After reaching at 800 °C, N_2 gas was changed to 100 % CO₂ gas to perform the carbonation process for 30 min. Then, the carbonated sample was calcined for 6 min under 100 % N_2 gas flow. The constant gas flow rate for CO₂ and N_2 was 40 ml/min. The CO₂ adsorption capacity was calculated using the following equation;

$$\text{CO}_2 \text{ adsorption capacity} = \frac{w_N - w_I}{w_I}$$

where w_N is the weight (%) of the carbonated sample after N cycle(s) and w_I is the initial weight (%) of the calcined sample, respectively.

Results and Discussion

Structural and Morphological Properties

Fig. 4 XRD patterns of (a) calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)_2) and (b) calcite (CaCO_3) prepared by precipitation and sol-gel methods as well as (c) natural limestone (CaCO_3).

Fig. 4 shows the XRD patterns of synthesized samples prepared by different methods and natural limestone. All of the major diffraction peaks in Fig. 4(a) matched well with the hexagonal phase calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)_2) according to the standard data (JCPDS-78-0135). The diffraction peaks located at $2\theta = 18^\circ$, 28° , 34° , 47° , 50° and 54° were corresponding to the (001), (100), (011), (012), (110) and (111) planes of Ca(OH)_2 phase, respectively (Hlaing et al., 2014). In addition, the minor diffraction peak at $2\theta = 29^\circ$ exhibited the presence of calcite phase.

When sol-gel method was conducted, rhombohedral phase calcite (CaCO_3) was observed (JCPDS-05-0586). In Fig. 4(b), diffraction peaks at 2θ of 23° , 29° , 36° , 39° , 43° , 47° , 48° and 57° were corresponding to (012), (104), (110), (113), (202), (018), (116), and (122) planes of calcite, respectively. No other impurity phases were detected. The strongest diffraction peak at $2\theta = 29^\circ$ was assigned to the (104) plane showed that calcite (CaCO_3) grew mainly along the (104) plane (Hlaing et al., 2015).

The XRD pattern of natural limestone collected from Taunggyi, Southern Shan State, Myanmar is shown in Fig. 4(c). All of the major diffraction peaks revealed that calcite was the principle mineral component of natural Plateau limestone. The minor diffraction peaks at 2θ value of 26° , 30° and 31° were corresponding to the quartz (SiO_2), dolomite ($\text{CaMg(CO}_3)_2$) and aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) phases, respectively. The crystallite sizes calculated by using Scherrer equation are listed in Table.1.

Table. 1 Structural and morphological properties of different calcium oxide based adsorbents.

Samples	Synthesis methods	Phases	Morphologies
Ca(OH) ₂	Precipitation	calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH) ₂)	Micro/nanostructure
CaCO ₃	Sol-gel	Calcite (CaCO ₃)	Nanoparticles
limestone	Collected from natural limestone	Calcite (CaCO ₃)	Compact solid structure

Fig. 5 (Cont.) FESEM images of (a) calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) and (b) calcite (CaCO_3) synthesized by precipitation and sol-gel methods as well as (c) natural limestone (CaCO_3).

The surface morphologies of CaO-based adsorbents were studied by FESEM. Fig. 5(a) exhibited the FESEM image of calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) prepared by precipitation method. As seen in Fig. 5(a), irregular-shaped and sized $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$ was observed. The result showed that room temperature was not suitable synthesized temperature to obtain homogenous micro or nanostructured $\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$.

Fig. 5(b) presents the FESEM image of calcite (CaCO_3) prepared by sol-gel method. As shown in the high magnification FESEM image (inset) in Fig 5(b), calcite (CaCO_3) nanoparticles were highly agglomerate. FESEM image in Fig. 5(c) shows compact surface of natural limestone (CaCO_3).

Thermal Properties

Fig. 6 TGA curve of calcium hydroxide ($\text{Ca}(\text{OH})_2$) prepared by precipitation method.

Fig. 7 TGA curves of (a) synthesized calcite (CaCO_3) prepared by sol-gel method and (b) natural limestone (CaCO_3) collected from Taunggyi, Southern Shan State, Myanmar.

Fig. 6 shows the TGA curve of calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)_2) prepared by precipitation method. Two steps of weight losses in Fig. 6 were discerned in the temperature ranges of 350 °C - 450 °C and 550 °C - 700 °C, respectively. Step I (350 °C - 450 °C) corresponded to the decomposition of Ca(OH)_2 , while step II (550 °C - 720 °C) was attributed to the decomposition of the presence of CaCO_3 . Fig. 7 shows the TGA curves of synthesized calcite (CaCO_3) and natural limestone (CaCO_3). The major weight losses between 650 °C and 850 °C in Fig. 7(a) and (b) were assigned to the decomposition of calcite CaCO_3 to CaO ($\text{CaCO}_3 \rightarrow \text{CaO} + \text{CO}_2$).

CO_2 adsorption capacities

Fig. 8 CO_2 adsorption capacities of CaO obtained from calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)_2), calcite (CaCO_3) and natural limestone (CaCO_3).

The CO_2 adsorption capacities of different CaO derived from calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)_2), calcite (CaCO_3) and natural limestone (CaCO_3) (denoted as CaO-Ca(OH)₂, CaO-

CaCO₃ and CaO-LM) are shown in Fig. 8. It could be seen that CaO obtained from different crystal structures and morphologies resulted in different CO₂ adsorption capacities. The capacities of CaO derived from synthesized calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) and calcite (CaCO₃) possessed high adsorption capacities.

However, CaO derived from natural limestone (CaCO₃) exhibited significantly lower CO₂ adsorption capacity when compared to CaO obtained from synthesized Ca(OH)₂ and CaCO₃. The results proved that synthesized CaO-based adsorbents had better adsorption capacity than natural limestone. The lower capacity of CaO obtained from natural limestone might be due to the larger and compact particle, which retarded the penetration of CO₂ during CO₂ adsorption. Therefore, further study needs to improve the adsorption capacity of CaO derived from natural limestone collected from Taunggyi, Southern Shan State, Myanmar.

Conclusion

In conclusion, the effects of crystal structures on CO₂ adsorption capacities of different CaO-based adsorbents were studied. The TGA results showed that CaO derived from micro/nanostructured calcium hydroxide (Ca(OH)₂) possessed the highest CO₂ adsorption capacity of 0.74 g-CO₂/g-adsorbent when compared to those of other CaO obtained from calcite (CaCO₃) nanoparticles and natural limestone (CaCO₃) (0.60 and 0.42 g-CO₂/g-adsorbent). This indicated that crystal structures and morphologies obviously affected the CO₂ adsorption capacities of CaO-based adsorbents.

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